

IDENTIFYING OUTLIERS IN POPULATION COHORTS: A BENCHMARK SCORE APPROACH WITH ML

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel framework for outlier detection based on group-specific predictions. A machine learning model is trained, and predictions are made for test groups using control and no-control techniques. Group predictions are compared to actual outcomes, and significant discrepancies are flagged as outliers. The framework leverages ML Hyperparameter tuning techniques to optimize model performance, enabling robust and automated detection of outlier groups.

Keywords: Outlier Detection, ML Hyperparameter Tuning

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I. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an innovative framework for detecting outliers that focuses on making predictions tailored to specific groups within a dataset. The proposed approach utilizes machine learning models to generate predictions for these groups, employing both control-based and no-control techniques to ensure a comprehensive comparison. Control-based techniques are particularly effective when data arrives in batches, as they leverage historical context to train models, allowing predictions to align closely with established trends. This historical training enables a robust understanding of the group's behavior under standard conditions, facilitating a more accurate assessment of what constitutes an outlier. In contrast, no-control techniques come into play when data is not available in batch form, indicating that there is little or no historical context for the incoming data. These techniques allow the model to adapt dynamically to real-time data streams, ensuring that outlier detection can occur even in environments characterized by variability and unpredictability.

Once predictions are generated for each group, they are compared against actual outcomes to determine if they are outliers. Significant deviations between predicted and observed outcomes are flagged as outliers using a binomial test, a statistical method that assesses the likelihood of observing such discrepancies under the assumption that the null hypothesis is true. This rigorous approach helps identify groups whose behavior deviates from expected norms, highlighting areas that may require further investigation or intervention. By leveraging binomial testing, the framework enhances the reliability of outlier detection, providing a quantitative basis for decision-making. This systematic comparison not only flags potential outliers but also aids in understanding the underlying patterns and dynamics within the data, offering insights that can drive further exploration and analysis.

To maximize the accuracy and reliability of the framework, hyperparameter tuning methods are employed. These techniques fine-tune the parameters of the machine learning model to optimize performance, thereby increasing the precision and robustness of the outlier detection process. Hyperparameter tuning is essential for achieving a high level of accuracy, as it allows the model to learn from the data more effectively and respond to its inherent complexities. The automated nature of this framework enables efficient outlier identification across large and complex datasets, making it suitable for applications where manual analysis would be impractical or insufficient. By combining group-specific analysis, advanced machine learning techniques, and automated processes, this framework proves to be adaptable and scalable. It offers a powerful tool for identifying and understanding outlier groups across various contexts, ultimately contributing to more informed decision-making and improved operational efficiency in data-driven environments.

II. KEY CONCEPTS

A. Outlier Detection

Outlier detection is a critical area of study in machine learning and data science, especially in population analysis where understanding anomalies can lead to significant insights. Outliers are data points that deviate considerably from the majority of the population. These deviations can either represent rare but meaningful occurrences or noise, depending on the context. For example, in healthcare, an outlier might signify a patient with an unusual disease progression, while in finance, it might point to fraudulent activity. Identifying these outlier groups is crucial for decision-making and predictive modeling, as failing to account for them can skew results and lead to misleading conclusions.

Outlier detection is a challenging task due to the complexity and diversity of the underlying causes of anomalies. There are various methods to detect outliers, ranging from statistical approaches to machine learning-based techniques. Statistical methods, such as z-scores or IQR (Interquartile Range), are some of the simplest ways to identify outliers by analyzing the distribution of the data and identifying points that lie far outside the expected range. However, these methods may not be sufficient when dealing with high-dimensional or complex datasets where relationships between variables are nonlinear.

Machine learning techniques, particularly clustering and density-based methods, offer more advanced solutions for outlier detection. Density-based clustering algorithms like HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) are particularly useful for identifying outlier groups in large, unstructured datasets. HDBSCAN works by identifying clusters based on the density of data points, where areas of low density are more likely to contain outliers.

Unlike traditional clustering algorithms like K-Means, HDBSCAN does not require the number of clusters to be specified beforehand, and it is capable of handling noise in the data. This makes it highly effective for real-world applications where the number of clusters or the presence of outliers is unknown.

Another technique for identifying outliers is the isolation forest, which is based on the idea that outliers are more susceptible to isolation than normal points. Isolation forests work by randomly partitioning the data into subspaces and building a decision tree based on these partitions. Since outliers are few and different, they are isolated more quickly, making this approach highly efficient for large-scale datasets.

In business applications, outlier detection plays a critical role in areas like fraud detection, customer segmentation, and risk management. For example, in financial services, identifying outlier transactions that deviate from a customer's typical spending behavior can help detect fraudulent activity. In retail, outlier groups in customer purchasing patterns may indicate niche markets or emerging trends that businesses can capitalize on. By isolating and studying these outlier groups, companies can make more informed decisions, such as adjusting marketing strategies or refining risk assessments.

In healthcare, detecting outlier patients—those who exhibit atypical symptoms or responses to treatments—can lead to earlier diagnoses of rare conditions or the identification of unusual drug side effects. Outlier detection is also critical in clinical trials, where unusual responses to treatments may skew the results and lead to incorrect conclusions about a drug's efficacy. By accounting for these outliers, researchers can ensure that their models provide more accurate and generalizable results.

One of the challenges in outlier detection is distinguishing between true outliers (those that represent meaningful deviations) and noise (data errors or random fluctuations). In highly sensitive fields like finance and healthcare, where the cost of false positives is high, this distinction becomes even more critical. Techniques like robust statistics, ensemble methods, and domain-specific knowledge are often employed to enhance the reliability of outlier detection algorithms.

In conclusion, outlier detection is an essential component of population analysis in machine learning. By identifying and understanding anomalous data points, businesses and researchers can gain insights that would otherwise be missed, leading to better decision-making and more accurate predictive models. Advanced techniques like density-based clustering and isolation forests have made it easier to detect and analyze outliers in large, complex datasets, further enhancing the ability of machine learning models to handle real-world challenges. As the amount of data grows, the importance of effective outlier detection will only continue to rise, especially in areas like fraud detection, healthcare, and risk management.

B. Binomial Test

Binomial testing is a statistical method used to determine whether the observed proportion of successes in a sample differs significantly from an expected proportion. It is particularly useful when the data consists of two possible outcomes, such as success/failure, pass/fail, or yes/no. This type of test can assess whether the observed frequency of an event matches a given probability.

Binomial testing is useful in situations where the data represents a series of independent trials, each with two possible outcomes, and you want to know whether the observed frequency of one outcome aligns with an assumed probability.

C. Machine Learning Overview and Tree-Based Models

Tree-based models are a highly influential and widely used class of machine learning algorithms known for their versatility and interpretability. At the core of these models is the idea of breaking down complex decision-making processes into a series of binary decisions, represented as branches in a tree structure. This approach makes tree-based models especially powerful for both classification and regression tasks, as they can handle diverse datasets with different types of features, including categorical and numerical variables.

A basic Decision Tree starts by selecting a feature that best splits the data into different classes or predicts a target variable in the case of regression. The feature that minimizes a loss function (such as Gini impurity for classification or mean squared error for regression) is chosen as the root node. The dataset is then split into subsets based on this feature, and the process is repeated recursively for each subset, creating branches of the tree. Each internal node in the tree represents a decision or a test on a feature, and each leaf node represents the final output or prediction. What makes Decision Trees particularly attractive is their interpretability—one can easily trace the path from the root to a leaf to understand how the model arrived at a specific prediction.

Despite their advantages, simple Decision Trees can easily overfit the training data. Since they are prone to capturing noise and small fluctuations in the data, they often perform poorly on unseen data. To counteract this, two popular ensemble methods—Random Forests and Gradient Boosting Trees—have been developed to enhance the robustness and accuracy of tree-based models.

Random Forests address the overfitting problem by creating a "forest" of trees, each of which is built on a random subset of the training data and a random selection of features. By introducing randomness in the tree-building process, Random Forests reduce the variance of the model. The predictions from each tree are aggregated (through majority voting for classification or averaging for regression) to produce a final output. This ensemble approach provides a more stable and accurate model by leveraging the wisdom of crowds, where many weak learners (individual trees) are combined to create a strong learner. Another benefit of Random Forests is their ability to handle missing data and their built-in feature importance mechanism, which allows users to understand which features contribute the most to the model's predictions.

Gradient Boosting Trees, on the other hand, take a different approach to improving model performance. Instead of building trees independently like in Random Forests, Gradient Boosting builds trees sequentially, with each new tree trying to correct the errors of the previous one. The idea is to minimize a loss function, such as classification error or mean squared error, by training each tree on the residuals (errors) of the previous trees. This iterative process produces a model that is highly accurate and effective at handling complex relationships in the data. However, Gradient Boosting Trees are more sensitive to overfitting and may require careful tuning of parameters such as learning rate, the number of trees, and tree depth.

Fig.1. Control Framework

One of the most well-known implementations of Gradient Boosting is XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting), which has gained popularity due to its speed and performance in handling large datasets. XGBoost introduces several innovations, such as regularization (to prevent overfitting), optimized tree-building techniques, and the ability to handle sparse data, making it one of the top choices for many machine learning competitions and real-world applications. Its capability to handle both classification and regression tasks efficiently and its flexibility in tuning hyperparameters make it a powerful tool in a data scientist's toolkit.

Despite their success, tree-based models are not without challenges. One limitation is their reliance on greedy algorithms for splitting the data, which may not always result in the best global model, as decisions made at higher levels of the tree can influence those made at lower levels. Additionally, tree-based models often require more computational resources compared to simpler models like linear regression. The need for extensive tuning in models like XGBoost can also be a barrier for beginners. However, the benefits of interpretability, scalability, and performance often outweigh these challenges, especially in complex real-world tasks where relationships between variables are nonlinear and difficult to model using simpler approaches.

In summary, tree-based models, whether in their basic form like Decision Trees or in advanced ensemble forms like Random Forests and Gradient Boosting Trees, offer a powerful approach to solving a wide variety of machine learning problems. Their ability to model complex, non-linear relationships while maintaining a level of interpretability makes them particularly useful in fields like finance, healthcare, and marketing. With advancements like XGBoost, these models continue to evolve, offering improved speed and accuracy, making them a staple in both academic research and industry applications.

II. FRAMEWORK DESIGN

In this approach, we utilize tree-based models for training, as they offer a robust method to capture the intricate relationships and patterns within data. Tree-based models, such as Random Forests or Gradient Boosted Trees, are particularly effective due to their ability to handle non-linear interactions and complex data structures. A key advantage of these models is their flexibility in managing missing data or variables that may not be relevant to a particular prediction. Even if certain variables are excluded or contain null values, tree-based models can adapt by redistributing the importance across other predictors, ensuring that the prediction process remains effective and unbiased. This adaptability allows the models to derive insights from the underlying patterns, making them ideal for scenarios where variables may be incomplete or selectively removed.

The training process involves two distinct scenarios depending on the availability and nature of historical data. In the first case, when historical data is available, we apply a control-based approach. This method leverages only historical data to train the model, enabling it to develop a nuanced understanding of past trends and patterns within the dataset. The trained model is then used to generate benchmark scores for a test group. These benchmark scores represent the model's expectations based on the historical data, providing a reference point to identify deviations or anomalies in the test group's performance. By using this control method, we can assess the test group against a well-understood historical baseline, helping to pinpoint areas where the test group's behavior diverges from expected norms.

The second scenario involves cases where the available data may not fully represent the subgroup or segment that is being tested for anomalies. Here, we intentionally exclude specific grouping variables when training the model, ensuring that the training data does not directly influence the outcome for that subgroup. By omitting the grouping variable(s), the model's training focuses on broader trends without being influenced by the specific characteristics of the segment being tested.

This approach is designed to detect anomalies by examining whether the test group's behavior deviates significantly from the patterns learned from the generalized data. This method is particularly useful for flagging anomalies when the segment being analyzed differs from the population used in training, as it allows the model to identify outliers without being biased by the segment-specific data during the training process.

In this approach, we use benchmark data as a "source of truth," serving as a reliable reference point to assess the performance of other data sets. The benchmark data represents established norms and expected behavior, while the actual data provides real-world observations, including trials, successes, and deviations from the expected outcomes. By comparing the two, we gain insights into how closely the actual results align with the established standards.

To quantify these comparisons, we apply a binomial test, a statistical method that evaluates whether the observed success rates in the actual data significantly deviate from what would be expected based on the benchmark data. This test allows us to assess the probability of observing a certain number of successes (or failures) given the known benchmark success rate. By setting predefined significance thresholds—such as 0.05, 0.01, or other p-values—we can determine whether the observed data falls within the expected range or if it significantly deviates from the benchmark. When a subgroup's results exceed the significance threshold, it is flagged as an outlier, indicating that the behavior or performance of this subgroup is notably different from what the benchmark data predicts.

Fig.2. No Control Framework

This methodology aligns with the core principle of outlier detection, which focuses on identifying deviations from a normal distribution or expected pattern. By introducing a structured framework that groups the data based on relevant variables—such as demographic characteristics, behavioral traits, or survey responses—we can pinpoint specific subgroups that diverge from the norm. This grouping-based framework enables a more granular analysis, revealing problem areas within a population that may not be evident when analyzing the entire dataset as a whole.

The approach proves particularly valuable in the context of survey analysis, where populations often exhibit significant variations in behavior, opinions, or outcomes. By identifying subgroups with notable deviations from the benchmark, we can highlight areas that may require further investigation or targeted interventions. For example, in a survey assessing customer satisfaction, this method could help identify demographic groups whose satisfaction levels deviate from the norm, allowing organizations to address their specific needs. Overall, the combination of benchmark comparisons and statistical testing offers a systematic way to detect outliers, ensuring that meaningful insights are drawn from complex data sets.

A. Control-Based Framework

Train Model: $f_{\text{control}}(X_{\text{historical}}) \rightarrow \widehat{y_{\text{historical}}}$

Where $X_{\text{historical}}$ represents the historical data and $\widehat{y_{\text{historical}}}$ historical are the predictions.

Benchmark Score: $S_{\text{benchmark}} = f_{\text{control}}(X_{\text{test}})$

where X_{test} is the test group data

Deviation Analysis:

$$\Delta_{\text{control}} = y_{\text{test}} - S_{\text{benchmark}}$$

where y_{test} is the observed outcome for the test group.

B. No-Control Framework

Train Model: $f_{\text{no-control}}(X \setminus G) \rightarrow \widehat{y_{\text{general}}}$

where XXX is the full dataset, GGG is the excluded grouping variable, and $\widehat{y_{\text{general}}}$ are the predictions based on generalized data.

Benchmark Score: $S_{\text{benchmark}} = f_{\text{control}}(X_{\text{test}})$

where X_{test} is the test group data.

Deviation Analysis:

$$\Delta_{\text{no-control}} = y_{\text{test}} - f_{\text{no-control}}(X_{\text{test}} \setminus G)$$

Binomial Test for the Outlier Detection

Hypothesis:

$$H_0: p = p_0$$

(Success rate is as expected)

$$H_1: p \neq p_0$$

(Success rate deviates from expectation)

Binomial Test Statistic:

$$P(X = k) = \binom{n}{k} p_0^k (1 - p_0)^{n-k}$$

where:

- n is the number of trials (sample size).
- k is the number of observed successes.
- p_0 is the benchmark success rate.

Significance Testing:

If $P(X \geq k | H_0) < \alpha$, reject H_0

where α is the significance level (e.g., 0.05 or 0.01).

Outlier Identification:

Flag as Outlier if Δ_{control} or $\Delta_{\text{no-control}}$

exceeds the threshold based on the binomial test.

III. RESULTS

Using the overall average as the benchmark or "source of truth" in a binomial test can introduce challenges, specifically leading to the risk of false positives and false negatives. A false positive occurs when a segment is incorrectly flagged as an outlier, even though its behavior is not significantly different from the norm.

This happens when the test overreacts to minor deviations from the overall average, mistakenly identifying them as significant anomalies. Conversely, a false negative arises when a segment with true deviations remains undetected. This typically happens when a real anomaly is masked by being compared to the overall average, which fails to highlight more subtle or localized deviations within the data.

To address these pitfalls, a more tailored framework is essential—one that allows us to analyze each segment in the context of its own characteristics rather than a broad overall average. By introducing a framework that segments the population based on relevant grouping variables (e.g., age, region, or demographic traits), we can perform more precise comparisons, reducing the likelihood of both false positives and false negatives. This method ensures that outliers are identified accurately, highlighting segments that truly differ from expected behavior without misclassifying those that fall within acceptable variance. It provides a more nuanced understanding of the data, ensuring that significant deviations are detected and brought to attention.

Beyond improving the accuracy of outlier detection, this approach offers additional benefits that are crucial for large-scale cohort analysis. By analyzing segments individually and comparing them against more relevant benchmarks, we can also build explanatory models that shed light on the factors driving variability in the target data. These models can reveal which characteristics or variables contribute most to the deviations seen in specific segments, providing valuable insights into why certain groups differ from others. For instance, a segment might deviate due to a particular socioeconomic factor, policy change, or regional trend, which the model can highlight for further investigation.

This method is especially critical when analyzing large cohorts, such as survey data or population studies, where significant diversity exists within the data. In such cases, a broad comparison to the overall average may miss localized issues, failing to address subgroups with unique patterns or needs. By adopting a more targeted framework, we can identify specific problem areas and outlier groups that require intervention or deeper analysis. This ensures that decision-makers have a clear understanding of which segments are driving unexpected trends, enabling more informed decisions and targeted actions. Ultimately, this approach not only refines the process of outlier detection but also empowers organizations to understand and address the root causes of variability in their data, leading to more effective strategies and better outcomes.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. C. Aggarwal, *Outlier Analysis*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2017. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-47578-3.
- [2] V. Chandola, A. Banerjee, and V. Kumar, "Anomaly Detection: A Survey," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 1-58, 2009. DOI: 10.1145/1541880.1541882.
- [3] V. J. Hodge and J. Austin, "A Survey of Outlier Detection Methodologies," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 85-126, 2004. DOI: 10.1023/B:0000045502.10941.a9.
- [4] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System," in *Proc. 22nd ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD)*, San Francisco, CA, USA, 2016, pp. 785-794. DOI: 10.1145/2939672.2939785.
- [5] H. Zhao, Z. Cai, Z. Zhang, T. Wang, and X. Zhang, "XGBoost Algorithm and Its Application in Machine Learning," in *Proc. 2021 IEEE 6th Int. Conf. Big Data Analytics (ICBDA)*, Xiamen, China, 2021, pp. 33-38. DOI: 10.1109/ICBDA51977.2021.9447520.
- [6] L. Xu and R. Goodacre, "On Splitting Training and Validation Set: A Comparative Study of Cross-Validation, Bootstrap, and Systematic Sampling for Estimating Prediction Error in QSAR Modeling," *J. Chemometrics*, vol. 32, no. 8, e2994, 2018. DOI: 10.1002/cem.2994.

- [7] W. J. Conover, Practical Nonparametric Statistics, 3rd ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1999.
- [8] R. J. G. B. Campello, D. Moulavi, and J. Sander, "Density-Based Clustering Based on Hierarchical Density Estimates," in Proc. 17th ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD), San Diego, CA, USA, 2013, pp. 160-172. DOI: 10.1145/2487575.2488173.
- [9] L. McInnes, J. Healy, and S. Astels, "hdbscan: Hierarchical Density Based Clustering," Journal of Open Source Software, vol. 2, no. 11, p. 205, 2017. DOI: 10.21105/joss.00205.
- [10] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," Machine Learning, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5-32, 2001. DOI: 10.1023/A:1010933404324.

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